

THE IMPACT OF FOOD PRICE FLUCTUATIONS AND COVID-19 ON FOOD PRICE STABILITY IN SUMATERA, INDONESIA

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Abstract

Food price fluctuations could affect food stability during the Covid-19 pandemic. This study aimed to analyze the long and short-term effects of food accessibility and Covid -19 on price stability or inflation in Sumatra. It used primary data for the monthly 2010M01-2020M12 period and secondary data from the Central Statistics Agency and the Ministry of Agriculture. The data were analyzed using Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (PARDL) - Pooled Mean Group (PMG) model. The results showed that both consumer rice and corn prices, except cassava, had a positive and significant short-term effect on food inflation in each province. In Sumatra, the effect was long and short-term aggregately. However, Covid -19 only indicated a negative and significant short-term relationship. These results indicate the necessity to optimize the supply chain system to maintain food supply sustainability and strengthen the farmers' adaptability to climate change.

Keywords: Food Accessibility, Covid -19, Food Stability, PARDL-PMG Model

1. Introduction

Food security has been a top priority worldwide for the last few decades. A good food security system promotes a country's economic growth and political stability towards prosperity (Schroeder dan Meyers 2016). In the first quarter of 2020, Indonesia experienced a Covid-19 pandemic that disrupted the food system. FAO (2020) reported that 130 million people would face severe hunger and 45 million people would experience food insecurity problems due to the pandemic.

Covid-19 influences food production and demand (Han et al., 2021). Sumatra is an Indonesian island with the second largest confirmed Covid-19 cases after Java. Between 37.70% and 47.04% of Sumatra's population experienced food insecurity from 2010 to 2018 (FSA 2020). Before the pandemic, the coefficient variation values for food inflation, rice, corn, cassava, and consumer sweet potato prices were 11.74%, 17.46%, 23.32%, 25.90%, and 33.32%, respectively. These values increased during the pandemic to 13.44 %, 17.64%, 24.33%, 25.98%, and 33.37% for food inflation and rice, consumer-level corn, cassava, and sweet potato prices, respectively. Strategic food commodities with coefficient variation values of 10-30% are classified as highly fluctuating and capable of influencing inflation rates (FSA 2020).

Areas without food reserves may not fulfill market demand, affecting food accessibility (Ma et al., 2021). In this case, accessibility is seen in the affordability or price of food (Capone et al., 2014). A significant price increase reduces household access to basic food (Akter and Basher 2014). The pandemic disrupts the local food supply chain, resulting in food instability and high inflation (FAO 2020). Food inflation is one indicator of food price stability (Widada and Mulyo, 2017). Studies on food inflation are interesting for several reasons. First, food inflation has a direct impact on consumers. Second, it deals directly with the political aspect, creating government policies and programs. Third, the shock is more volatile and persistent and transmits into non-food inflation with a stronger and lasting effect (Ismaya and Anugrah 2018).

Few studies have examined the effect of rising prices and Covid-19 on Indonesia's and global food price stability. Laili et al. (2022) found that garlic and cayenne pepper price fluctuations contributed to rising food commodity prices during the Covid 19 pandemic in Indonesia. Fluctuations in the prices of chicken meat and eggs also caused food inflation during the pandemic (Baladina et al., 2021). Moreover, Karnowahadi et al. (2021) found that the price fluctuations of shallots and Covid-19 affected the food price stability in Semarang. Agyei et al. (2020) found that the increase in corn prices and pandemic affected the price stability of most countries in Africa. According to Erokhin and Gao (2020), food price fluctuations and Covid-19 affected price inflation in 45 developing countries.

This study aimed to analyze the short and long-term impact of fluctuations in rice, corn, cassava, and sweet potato consumer prices and the Covid-19 pandemic on food price stability or inflation in Sumatra. The results complement the limitations of previous studies in several ways. First, this study focused on rice, corn, cassava, and sweet potatoes. These food commodities were chosen because they contribute two-thirds of human calories and carbohydrates (Zhao et al. 2017), especially during the Covid-19 pandemic. Second, the study analyzed the relationship between major food commodities and food price stability during the pandemic by looking at their short and long-term effects. Third, the sample studied used differences in economic conditions and structure. This study emphasized regional heterogeneity using dynamic panel data modeling called Pooled Mean Group, which has been rarely used in previous studies.

2. Methodology

2.1 Data and Variables

The panel data approach was used with monthly data for the 2010M01 to 2020M12 period in ten provinces on the island of Sumatra. The data were sourced from the Central Statistics Agency and the Indonesian Ministry of Agriculture. The study also used the variables of consumer-level rice price (HKBE), corn price (HKJA), cassava price (HKUK), and sweet potato price (HKUJ). The indicator of food price stability was food inflation (INBP), while the Covid-19 pandemic was used as a dummy variable.

2.2 Unit Root Test

The two types of unit root tests used are Levin Lin Chu (LLC) and Breitung. LLC assumes that all autoregressive are considered equal in time series and cross-section data (Levin et al. 2002). The Breitung test evaluates the correlation between units with various transformations based on the estimation of an independent regression system (Breitung 2000).

2.3 Panel Model Autoregressive Distributed Lag (PARDL)

The PARDL model was used to analyze the long and short-term effects of staple food prices (accessibility) and the Covid-19 pandemic on food inflation (stability). The PARDL model is described as follows:

$$\Delta \text{INBP}_{it} = (\alpha_i \text{INBP}_{i,t-1} + \gamma'_{1i} \text{HKBE}_{it} + \gamma'_{2i} \text{HKJA}_{it} + \gamma'_{3i} \text{HKUK}_{it} + \gamma'_{4i} \text{HKUJ}_{it} + \gamma'_{5i} \text{COV19}_{it}) + \sum_{j=1}^{p-1} \delta_{ij}^* \Delta \text{INBP}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi_{1ij}^* \Delta \text{HKBE}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi_{2ij}^* \Delta \text{HKJA}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi_{3ij}^* \Delta \text{HKUK}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi_{4ij}^* \Delta \text{HKUJ}_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^{q-1} \phi_{5ij}^* \Delta \text{COV19}_{i,t-j} + \mu_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Unit Root Test Results

Table 1 shows the results of Levin Lin Chu (LLC) and Breitung unit root tests for the five variables at the level I(0). The results are insignificant ($p > 0.05$), supporting the null hypothesis. Furthermore, a stationary test was conducted at the first difference degree I(1) because it is not stationary at level I(0). The results showed that the five variables are stationary and reject the null hypothesis, which is not stationary.

Table 1: Unit root test

Variable	LLC Test		Breitung Test	
	Level	First Difference	Level	First Difference
INBP	-0.4318	-20.4852***	-5.9871	-24.8079***
HKBE	-50772	-20.1289***	4.8206	-21.2428***
HKJA	-0.4472	-22.0194***	6.0295	-25.1994***
HKUK	-2.2288	-21.5928***	0.8982	-25.7491***
HKUJ	-2.3424	-23.1322***	2.4266	-26.0969***

*Statistical significance at 10%, **statistical significance at 5%, ***statistical significance at 1%

3.2 Results of Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (PARDL) – PMG Model

The estimation results of the PMG model PARDL test comprise two long and short-term relationships. The variable of consumer-level rice price for Aceh, Bangka Belitung, and Riau provinces has a positive and significant short-term relationship with food inflation.

The variable of consumer-level corn price for West Sumatra, Bengkulu, Lampung, and Riau provinces has a positive and significant short-term relationship with food inflation. Similar results were found for the variable of consumer-level cassava price for the North Sumatra, Bengkulu, and Bangka Belitung provinces.

Table 2: Test on Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (PARDL) with Pooled Mean Group (PMG) model

Short-term estimation (full sample)					
Variable	Aceh	North Sumatra	West Sumatra	Riau	Jambi
ECT	-0.0965** (0.013)	-0.0742*** (0.006)	-0.1361*** (0.002)	-0.0851*** (0.007)	-0.0574* (0.100)
HKBE	0.0060* (0.062)	0.0016 (0.676)	0.0011 (0.808)	0.0032 (0.361)	0.0014 (0.571)
HKJA	-0.0001 (0.827)	0.0002 (0.736)	0.0012* (0.088)	0.0008 (0.224)	-0.0005 (0.302)
HKUK	-0.0086*** (0.000)	0.0090*** (0.000)	0.0121 (0.102)	0.0023 (0.556)	0.0067 (0.111)
HKUJ	0.0007 (0.813)	0.0057 (0.207)	0.0089 (0.152)	0.0036 (0.206)	-0.0004 (0.785)
COV19	0.1566 (0.974)	-0.7919 (0.904)	-1.8716 (0.848)	-1.6545 (0.788)	-0.5139 (0.937)
Variable	South Sumatra	Bengkulu	Lampung	Bangka Belitung	Riau Islands
ECT	-0.0068 (0.592)	-0.0857*** (0.009)	-0.0259 (0.122)	-0.0290* (0.082)	-0.0645** (0.017)
HKBE	0.0017 (0.485)	-0.0008 (0.839)	0.0003 (0.920)	0.0083* (0.066)	0.0075*** (0.009)
HKJA	0.00003 (0.962)	0.0010* (0.052)	0.0011** (0.019)	-0.0003 (0.562)	0.0018*** (0.006)
HKUK	-0.0269*** (0.000)	0.0232*** (0.001)	-0.0071 (0.190)	0.0177*** (0.000)	-0.0017 (0.752)
HKUJ	-0.0046 (0.396)	-0.0004 (0.934)	-0.0037 (0.317)	-0.0078 (0.131)	-0.0017 (0.681)
COV19	-2.5168 (0.726)	-2.3796 (0.718)	-1.4459 (0.817)	-0.2527 (0.966)	-3.0587 (0.674)
Variable	Long term estimation			Short term estimation	
ECT	-			-0.0661***(0.000)	
HKBE	0.0138***(0.000)			0.0030***(0.002)	
HKJA	0.0023***(0.000)			0.0005**(0.032)	
HKUK	-0.0036(0.426)			0.0026(0.561)	
HKUJ	-0.0025(0.346)			0.000019(0.990)	
COV19	3.9632(0.736)			-1.4329***(0.000)	

*signifikansi statistik pada 10%, **signifikansi statistik at 5%, ***statistical significance at 1%

However, the consumer-level cassava price has a negative and significant long-term relationship with food price inflation in Aceh and South Sumatra provinces. The variable of

consumer rice and corn prices has a positive and significant relationship with food inflation in Sumatra in the long and short term. The Covid-19 variable has a negative and significant short-term relationship with food inflation. Table 2 shows the results of the Panel Autoregressive Distributed Lag (PARDL) test with the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) model.

3.3 Short-Term Relationship between Food Price Fluctuations and Covid-19 on Food Price Stability in Sumatra

The increase in the rice, corn, and cassava consumer prices increased food price inflation in Aceh, Bangka Belitung, Riau Islands, West Sumatra, Lampung, North Sumatra, and Bengkulu. This result is consistent with previous studies that rice prices in some of these areas increased because rice has become a primary need in the short term (Kusumah and Wibawa, 2017; Nairobi and Caroline, 2021). The short-term increase in rice prices is because most people depend on rice as the main food for carbohydrate fulfillment (Fitrawaty et al., 2020). These findings also support Widarjono and Rucbha (2016) that corn prices increase in the short term because it is consumed by most households in Sumatra compared to rice. The short-term increase in rice, corn, and tuber prices were also driven by low supply (Anugrah and Pratama 2019). Cassava commodity in Aceh and South Sumatra was significant in the short term but negatively impacted food inflation. This is because Indonesia is the world's third producer of tuber products, especially cassava. The country has imported tuber products continuously from 2009-2018 to prevent an increase in food inflation in certain months due to insufficient supply (Ministry of Agriculture 2020). Importation helps fulfill domestic demand and suppress prices.

The short-term increase in the rice and corn prices in some areas led to food shortages and inflation. This is in line with TNP2K (2020) that the main causes of food price inflation are scarcity and limited supplies or stocks. Inflation in Sumatra is formed based on the contribution or dependence between adjacent regions. This is consistent with Ahmad et al. (2019) that inflation in the nearest province contributes to inflation in other provinces, creating spatial dependence. The regional spatial dependence is formed due to production factors and the movement of strategic food commodities such as rice, corn, and tubers.

The Covid-19 pandemic contributes to a short-term decline in food price inflation. This finding is consistent with Wahidah dan Antriyandarti (2021) that an increase in Covid-19 cases would contribute to layoffs (PHK) in companies, industries, and offices, increasing unemployment. Inflation decreases with increased unemployment, according to the Phillips curve theory. Similarly, Yuniarti et al. (2021) stated that the increase in Covid-19 reduced inflation by -0.01%. The weakening inflation was caused by decreased economic activity due to increased layoffs and the Work from Home (WFH) scheme.

3.4 Long-Term Relationship between Food Price Fluctuations and Covid-19 on Food Price Stability in Sumatra

The findings indicated that rice is the main commodity that affects food price stability in the long term. This is in line with Fitriani (2019) that the long-term increase in rice prices is caused by scarcity due to climate change and the decline in supply by farmers and producers. From 1983 to 2019, Indonesia recorded an average rice import volume of 966.62 thousand tons or an

increase of 46.13%. Rice prices between 1983 and 2020 increased at 11.32% yearly, contributing to the rise in food inflation. The results showed that increased corn prices contributed to higher food inflation. These findings are consistent with Fadhilah et al. (2020) that high demand, limited production, and high domestic prices trigger food inflation. Furthermore, Wahyudi et al. (2017) showed that high demand increased consumer corn prices and food inflation in Indonesia, including Sumatra. The increase in food prices was also caused by restrictions on national corn imports during the 2015-2019 period by the government. This was because domestic corn production was abundant and could be absorbed by the consumption sector. However, the price of corn at the consumer level increased significantly in the same year. This was because consumers bore the costs of the import ban policy.

The long-term effect of Covid-19 on food stability is positive but insignificant. This finding is consistent with Bonam and Smadu (2021) for several reasons. First, the government is involved in measures to stimulate the economy on a large scale to avoid mass business and industrial layoffs and bankruptcies. Monetary policy is directed to be more accommodative, such as preventing credit crunches and liquidity shortages. These policies largely mitigate the negative economic impact of the pandemic. However, this could lead to rising inflation in the long term when maintained after the pandemic. Second, the government's vaccination efforts have slowed the opening of the lockdown. This may lead to a rebound as households reopen their savings and release large demand.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

In the short and long term, food stability in Sumatra is influenced by rice, corn, and cassava prices and the Covid-19 pandemic. In the short term, consumer-level rice and cassava prices have a positive and strong relationship with food stability. Rice and corn also have a strong and positive relationship with food stability in the long and short term. In contrast, the Covid-19 pandemic has a negative and significant short-term relationship with food stability. The pandemic has a unidirectional but insignificant relationship with food price stability.

The rice price increased in the short term because the commodity is a primary need and staple food to fulfill carbohydrate needs. Corn prices also increased because it was consumed by most households in Sumatra compared to rice. The price of tubers, corn, and rice increased mainly due to low supply. The short-term increase in rice and corn prices was caused by scarcity and limited stock. In contrast, the long-term increase in the aggregate price of rice and maize was caused by climate change, decreased supply from farmers, high demand, limited production, and high domestic market prices. Higher price fluctuations cause uncertainties among consumers regarding the future. This requires strengthening strategic food logistics distribution channels in each region to overcome the scarcity problem. Furthermore, the supply chain system should be optimized to maintain a sustainable strategic food supply by producers, distributors, retailers, and consumers. Climate change also causes food price fluctuations in various regions. Therefore, the adaptive capacity of farmers and the government should be strengthened using new technology, maximum infrastructure use, and proper irrigation water

management. Further studies could examine the relationship of food price fluctuation with other dimensions, such as food availability.

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